

Fig. 1. SDS-polyacrilamide gel electrophoresis pattern of: defatted seed protein fraction, 50 μ g (a); and water-soluble fraction of defatted seed, 15 μ g (b) and 100 μ g (c).

stearic acid, oleic acid, linoleic acid and linolenic acid using GLC by converting them into their respective methyl-esters. The non-fatty acid fraction isolated from this was found to contain β -sitosterol (m.p. 137-38 $^{\circ}$ and $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 35^{\circ}$) and an unidentified compound. The seed oil is reported to have some purgative effect² which needs some pharmacological studies. Considering all the above mentioned remarkable characteristics of the seed kernel, further studies on it are in progress.

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Heterocyclic Systems, Part I. Reactions of 2, 3-Dichloroquinoxaline with Cyclic Thioureas, Dithiocarbamates and Thioamides

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IN continuation to our earlier work^{1,2}, now syntheses of II, III, IV and V have been accomplished. I when condensed with 2-thiobarbituric acid in absolute alcohol yielded II, whereas with 4-methyl-2-mercapto imidazoline furnished III. Since 4-methyl-2-mercapto imidazoline is an unsymmetrical thiourea it is likely to yield 2-methyl-2,3-dihydro imidazo[2',1':2,3]thiazolo[4,5-b]quinoxaline(III) or its 3-methyl isomer. However since only one compound was obtained (TLC), it has been assigned the structure (III) on analogy with our earlier work³, but needs confirmation. Thiazolo-quinoxalines (IV) and (V) were synthesized by the reactions of I with substituted ammonium dithiocarbamates and thioamides in presence of fused sodium acetate in absolute ethanol. Structures II, III, IV and V have been characterized by IR spectra (*vide experimental*).

1. 2-Thiobarbituric Acid, EtOH;
2. 4-Methyl-2-mercapto-imidazoline, EtOH;
3. RNECBSNH₄, EtOH, NaOAc;
4. RCSNH₂, EtOH, NaOAc.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were taken in Nujol mull. TLC was performed on silicagel plates using acetone-benzene (1:3) as solvent system.

3H-Pyrimidino[2',1':2,3]thiazolo [4,5-b]quinoxaline-2,4-dione (II):

A solution of I (1.00 g, 0.005 mole) and 2-thiobarbituric acid (0.72 g, 0.005 mole) in anhydrous

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ethanol (25 ml) was refluxed on a steam bath for about 6-7 hours. The reaction mixture acquired orange colour and an orange-brown solid separated, which was filtered, washed with 5% sodium bicarbonate solution and finally with water. The compound was purified by dissolving in sodium carbonate solution and then reprecipitating with acetic acid, m.p. $>290^\circ$, yield 0.6 g (44%), $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) 1710, 1650, 1600, 1530, 1150, 755. (Found: S, 11.34; N, 20.46. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_6\text{N}_4\text{SO}_2$, S, 11.85; N, 20.74%).

2-Methyl-2, 3-dihydro-imidazo[2'. 1' : 2, 3]thiazolo [4,5-b]quinoxaline(III) :

A solution of I (1.00 g, 0.005 mole) and 4-methyl-2-mercapto imidazoline (0.58 g, 0.005 mole) in absolute ethanol (25 ml) was heated on a steam bath for about 5 hours. The yellow coloured solid thus obtained was filtered, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and then with water. Crystallization from DMF afforded yellow micro-needles, m.p. $>300^\circ$, yield 0.4 g (33%), $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) 1610, 1555, 1335, 1260, 1120, 755. (Found: S, 12.92. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{S}$, S, 13.22%).

2-Thio-thiazolo[4,5-b]quinoxaline(IV, R = H) :

It was prepared by refluxing a solution of I (1.0 g, 0.005 mole), ammonium dithiocarbamate (0.55 g, 0.005 mole), and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.82 g) in absolute ethanol (30 ml) for 3 hours. The yellow coloured solid was filtered, washed with water and crystallized from DMF m.p. $>300^\circ$, yield 0.7 g (64%), $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) 3170, 3090, 1615, 1570, 1150, 835, 740. (Found: S, 28.84. Calcd. for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{S}_2$, S, 29.22%). Similarly were prepared IV(R = o-HO-C₆H₄), m.p. $>290^\circ$, $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) 3170-3040, 1610, 1555, 1265, 1140, 825, 755. (Found: S, 20.14. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_9\text{N}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$, S, 20.58%). IV(R = m-NO₂-C₆H₄), m.p. $>290^\circ$, (Found: S, 19.95. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$, S, 19.69%).

Thiazolo [4,5-b] quinoxalineV(R = H) :

It was synthesized by reacting equimolecular proportions of I and thioamides in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate in ethanol in the manner described above m.p. $>280^\circ$, $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) 3100, 1610, 1485, 1330, 1160, 755. (Found: S, 16.68. Calcd. for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{S}$, S, 17.11%). Similarly were prepared V(R = CH₃), m.p. $>290^\circ$ (Found: S, 16.33. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{S}$, S, 15.92%), V(R = C₆H₅), m.p. $>290^\circ$ (Found: S, 11.87. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_9\text{N}_2\text{S}$, S, 12.16%). V(R = m-NO₂-C₆H₄), m.p. $>290^\circ$ (Found: S, 9.86. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{SO}_2$, S, 10.39%).

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Synthesis of O, O-Dialkyl-S-[3-(Aryloxymethyl)-4-Substituted Phenyl-1,2,4-Triazol-5-yl]-Dithiophosphate as Possible Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) Inhibitors and Bactericides

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ORGANOPHOSPHATES have been extensively used as insecticides^{1,2} and exhibit antiacetylcholinesterase activities^{3,4}. A number of substituted triazoles are good bactericides^{5,6}, fungicides⁷⁻⁹ and herbicides^{10,11}. Triazoles with phenoxy methyl moiety are expected to have increased pesticidal activities as phenoxy acetic acid itself has been associated with various biological activities^{12,13}. In the present communication we have condensed several substituted triazoles with O,O-dialkyl chlorothiophosphate in order to synthesise O,O-dialkyl-S-[3-(aryloxymethyl)-4-substituted phenyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl]-dithiophosphates (I, Table 1) and tested for their biological activities.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The synthesised compounds have been characterised by ir spectroscopy and elemental analysis.

O, O-Dialkylchlorothiophosphate was prepared by known method of Fletcher *et al*¹⁴. Thiophosphoryl chloride was prepared according to the method of Moellar¹⁵. The key intermediate substituted triazoles have been prepared by known procedure¹⁶.

O, O-Dialkyl-S-[3-(4-Chlorophenoxy methyl)-4-Phenyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl]-dithiophosphate :

O,O-Dialkylchlorothiophosphate (0.01 M) and 3-(4-chlorophenoxy methyl)-5-mercapto-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazole (0.01 M) was refluxed in dry acetone